

Research Article

Heavy Metals Bioremediation of Agricultural Soil Using Poultry Litter

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to determine the level of heavy metals contamination of agricultural soil and to reduce its concentration in the soil using poultry litter. Soil sampled at Inua Eyet Ikot, Mkpnanak, Ibeno Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State was analyzed to check for the initial heavy metal concentration of the soil. Poultry litter as a nutrient additive bearing microorganisms, bacteria, and fungi was introduced to the soil to reduce the concentration of heavy metals. The sampled soil was mixed with poultry litter at three different proportions i.e. poultry litter (PL) to crude oil contaminated soil (COCS) namely PL 20% + COCS, PL 40% + COCS and PL 50% + COCS. Heavy metals Copper(Cu), Iron (Fe), Manganese (Mn), Lead (Pb), Cadmium (Cd), Arsenic (As), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni) concentration in the soil before and after 8 weeks were measured and analyzed by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) analysis which was carried out using wet oxidation method (digestion) for soils. The treatment category PL 50% + COCS proved to be more effective in the reduction of heavy metals in the soil as it reduced Copper, Iron, Manganese, Lead, Cadmium, Arsenic, Chromium and Nickel by 87.5%, 92.2%, 93.37%, 49.72%, 67%, 66.8%, 76.1% and 73.7%. Reductions in all treatment categories were statistically analyzed by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and were found to be significantly different from the untreated soil at probability value $P < 0.05$, with the significance level at 95%. The research findings indicate that poultry litter, which has microorganisms in it, enhances reduction of the concentration of heavy metals in contaminated soils.

Keywords: Heavy metals, Poultry litter, Bioremediation, Crude oil contaminated soil (COCS), Microorganisms.

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Introduction

Environmental degradation is assuming an alarming rate worldwide. This could be linked to indiscriminate disposal of crude oil into gutters, water drains, open vacant plots and farms is a common practice in Nigeria (Okonokhua *et al.*, 2007). Heavy metals such as Vanadium, Lead, Aluminium, Nickel and Iron usually below detectable limits in unused lubricating oil have been reported by (Whisman *et al.*, 1971) to give high values (part per million -ppm) in used oil. These metals may be retained in soils in the form of Oxides, Hydroxides, Carbonates, Exchangeable Cations, and/or bound to the organic matter in the soil (Yong *et al.*, 1992). This problem might not be unconnected with the rapid industrialization, population growth and technological advancement being experienced in most parts of the world today. A long list of potentially hazardous substances is released on a daily basis which contributes to the global pollution burden. As part of this 'list', are heavy metals resulting from industrial wastes; electronic wastes, oil spills etc., and they pose a serious threat to both man and animals if not properly treated (Okonokhua *et al.*, 2007).

The term heavy metal refers to any metallic chemical element that has a relatively high density and is toxic or poisonous at high concentrations. Examples of heavy metals that are harmful to humans include Mercury, Lead, and Arsenic. (Roane, 1999). Chronic exposure to these metals can have serious health consequences. Humans are exposed to heavy metals through inhalation of air pollutants, consumption of contaminated drinking water, exposure to contaminated soils or industrial waste, or consumption of contaminated food grown on contaminated land. Food sources such as vegetables, grains, fruits, fish and shellfish can become contaminated by accumulating metals from surrounding soil and water. Heavy metal exposure causes serious health effects, including reduced growth and development, cancer, organ damage, nervous system damage, and in extreme cases, death (Roane, 1999).

The commonly employed methods of treating heavy metals contaminated soils includes precipitation and ion exchange but these methods remain limited in the treatment of the contamination by heavy metals (Kratochvil, 1997). Over the last decade, biosorption was developed as an alternative treatment method for the remediation of heavy metals contaminated soils (Volesky, 1990; Williams, 1998). This technology involves the accumulation of heavy metals by biological material either by metabolically mediated methods or by purely physicochemical means (Sakaguchi and Nakijama, 1991). Unlike physical and chemical soil remediation methods, biosorption is relatively cheap (Volesky, 1990; Williams, 1998); and relies on active microbial presence and metabolism which in some environmental matrices is inhibited by nutrient availability and bioavailability as

there exists a direct relationship between nutrient supply and microbial growth (Sakaguchi and Nakijama, 1991). This study tends to adopt bioremediation method in trying to address the incidence of heavy metals contamination of agricultural soils as a result of recorded crude oil spillage at the Mkpanak Community, in Ibeno Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom between 2016 and 2017, Ikenna (2016). The spillage incidence has led to depletion in the nutrient status (nitrogen and phosphorus) of the soil, inhibition of microbial activities, crop growth and crop survival as has been studied in other crude oil-contaminated sites (Atlas and Bartha, 1993; Kirk *et al.*, 2005). The resultant effect is a waxy texture in the contaminated soil with spilled crude oil as it is in Mkpanak Community, (Anoliefo and Vwioko, 1995). Poultry litter is employed in this study to be used in attempting to reduce heavy metal concentration in the study area soil through the method of bioremediation due to ease of its affordability and availability.

Bioremediation, the method used in this study is inexpensive, is considered natural, socially acceptable and environmentally friendly compared with other approaches. The technology will help minimize the prohibitive cost associated with soil remediation, prevent significant soil texture alteration, prevent the transfer of pollutants from one medium to another and ensure a healthier technique for remediating heavy metals. In effect, this method seeks to leverage on its cost effectiveness when compared to other methods, in remediating heavy metals from soil as a result of crude oil contamination using microbial consortia from poultry litter (Okonokhua *et al.*, 2007). This method is interesting and innovating considering the common problems associated with conventional treatment methods such as precipitation and ion exchange, which includes; the difficulties encountered in treating the solid waste subsequently generated might not exist since biological treatment concentrates the wastes into smaller volume (Okonokhua *et al.*, 2007) which are subsequently easier to dispose of appropriately (Bhide *et al.*, 1996). Two approaches have been applied to enhance decontamination of soils with petroleum products. These are: ex- situ, which involves removal of the polluted soil (excavation), transport to and cleaning (washing) in a technical plant procedure and in-situ, which involves clean-up at the site itself (Merkl, 2005; Van Gestel and Kamerman, 1992). Microorganisms are the principal agents responsible for the recycling of carbon in nature. (Atlas and Bartha, 1993) observed that in many soils, there is already an adequate indigenous hydrocarbonoclastic microbial community, capable of extensive oil biodegradation provided that the environmental conditions are favourable for oil-degrading metabolic activity. It was suggested by some researchers (Shailubhai, 1986; Atlas and Bartha, 1993) that all soils except those that are very acidic, contained the organisms capable of degrading oil products, and that the problem was actually one of supplying the necessary nutrients at the site. According to Gibson (1982), the ability of microorganisms to utilise hydrocarbons is widely distributed among diverse microbial

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populations. Many species of bacteria, cyanobacteria, filamentous fungi, and yeasts co-exist in natural ecosystems and may act independently or in combination to metabolize aromatic hydrocarbons. Some of the common microbial genera that can degrade hydrocarbons in the soil were suggested by Shailubhai, (1986). The overall effect of an organism on a complex substrate is measured by its capacity to attack only certain substances or to accumulate intermediates that it cannot degrade. Gibson (1982) observed that extensive degradation of petroleum pollutants generally was accomplished by mixed microbial populations, rather than single microbial species. Combinations of bacteria and fungi provided more degradation of mixed hydrocarbon substrates unlike bacterial or fungi strains acting individually.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

Mkpanak Community situated Ibeno Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State lies (Wikipedia, 2017) between Latitude 04° 20' to 04° 32'N and Longitude 08° 0' to 08° 1'E of the Greenwich Meridian. The area is located on the coastal plain sand of South Eastern Nigeria and is within the mangrove and fresh water swamp forest belt Figure 1a. The area has rain throughout the year with a peak between May and September. The climatic condition in Ibeno is favorable all year round for fishing and farming. The main occupation of the people is fishing; however, farming and petty trading is also very common. The average temperature, wind speed and relative humidity of the study area is about 83°F (28°C), 5mph (8km/h) and 70% respectively (Wikipedia, 2017; Inyang, 1978). The soil is a sandy loam. The mean sand, silt and clay content 0.7cm – 15cm over depth were 820, 60 and 120 g/kg respectively. The average slope of the site is less than 5%. More than 80% of the total annual rainfall is received between the months of May and October with the mean annual total in excess of 1700mm (The Forestry Management, Evaluation and Coordinating Unit - FORMECU, 1998). The mean annual maximum temperature varies from 27°C to 32°C in the period from March to May. The mean daily sunshine hours in the area are between 5 hours and 6 hours in the dry season and 3 to 5 hours in the wet season (Inyang, 1978).

Figure 1a: Akwa Ibom State showing Study Area

Field Sampling

Soil sample from Inua Eyet Ikot, Mkpanak Community was collected (Figure 1b), at the depth of 0.7cm – 15cm using an auger into a plastic container for onward analysis, (Inyang, 1978). The coordinates of the soil sampling point at Mkpanak falls within Latitude 04° 33.148°N to 04°33.153'N and Longitude 08° 33.180'E to 08°00.182°E. Poultry droppings were collected at the University of Uyo Teaching and Research Farm located at Use Offot, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Figure 1b: Crude oil contaminated site showing Study Area and Sample Location

Experimental Design

The air-dried crude oil contaminated soil (COCS) samples were measured and three plastic buckets used as test cells. The plastic buckets contained soil mixed thoroughly with poultry litter in three separate proportions i.e. 80% weight of soil (1.6 kg) to 20% weight of poultry litter (0.4 kg), 50% weight of soil (1.0 kg) to 50% weight of poultry litter (1.0 kg) and 60% weight of soil (1.2 kg) to 40% weight of poultry litter (0.8 kg) and labeled as PL 20% + COCS (Poultry Litter + Crude Oil Contaminated Soil), PL 50% + COCS and PL 40% + COCS and Soil respectively (Bade *et al.*, 2012). Each bucket was watered as necessary to achieve optimum moisture requirement of 17% for microbial growth. The soil sample was kept in a plastic container under stable conditions to prevent any environmental effect on it that could include high temperature and airborne impurities (Swanell, *et al.*, 1996). There are two major approaches to bioremediation which are; bioaugmentation, the method employs known oil – degrading microorganisms which are added to supplement the existing microbial population and biostimulation, a method in which the growth of indigenous oil degraders is stimulated by the addition of nutrients (Bade *et al.*, 2012). Bioaugmentation approach was employed in this study work using poultry litter. The various parameters determined, reagent used, model adopted and references are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters determined from the soil and poultry litter constituent

S/N	Tested Parameter(s)	Reagent used	Model Adopted	References
1	Particle size distribution	Sodium hexametaphosphate (HMP)	$\frac{\text{Oven dry Silt mass}}{\text{Total Subsample mass}}$	Gee and Bauder 1986
2	Bulk Density	Sodium hexametaphosphate (HMP)	$\frac{\text{Mass of oven dry soil (g)}}{\text{Volume of bulk soil (cm}^3\text{)}}$	Black and Hartge 1986
3	Soil Moisture	Drying Oven	$M_n = (W_w - W_d) / W_w \times 100$	Nancy and Tom 1996
4	Hydraulic Conductivity	Constant - Head Permeameter	$K_{sat} = \frac{QL}{AT\Delta H}$	Klute and Dirksen, 1986
5	Microbiological analysis		Serial Dilution of Samples	Prescott et. al., 2005
6	Estimation of microbial load from the samples	Media: Nutrient Agar (NA), Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA), MacCoukey agar (MCA) and Re-enforced Clostridium agar (RCA).	Methods: Pour plate, spread plate and vapour plate	Harrigan and McCance, 1976
7	Incubation of Culture Plates and Counting of Microbial Colonies	Gallenkamp Incubator, Quebec colony counter	Incubated at room temperature for 21 days and enumeration of microbial colonies	Harrigan and McCance, 1976
8	Purification and Maintenance of Microbial Isolates	Media: Nutrient Agar	Representative colonies from culture plates were picked for characterization	Cheesbrough, 2004
9	Characterization and Identification of	Bergey's manual of Determinative Bacteriology	Collection and identification of various isolated bacteria	Robert et.al., 1994 ; Barnett and Barry (1987)

	Microbial Isolates				
10	pH Analysis	Digital pH meter			
11	Heavy Metals Analysis	Nitric acid and Hydrochloric acid.	Fume chamber and Absorption Spectrometer	Atomic	American Public Health Association (APHA, 2000).

Where M_n = moisture content (%) of material n , W_w = wet weight of the sample (g), W_d = weight of the sample (g) after drying; K_{sat} is the Saturated hydraulic conductivity, Q is the volume of water (cm^3) that flow through a cross - sectional area A (cm^2) in time T (sec) and ΔH is the hydraulic head difference imposed across the core sample of length L (cm).

One - way ANOVA at a 95% significance level was used to compare the level of effectiveness of the three treatment categories in the proportions PL 20%, PL 40% and PL 50% in remediating the crude oil contaminated soil (COCS).

Results and Discussion

Particle size analysis shows that the site is sandy loam. The sand, silt and clay particle size distribution ranged from 654 - 818, 21 - 100 and 121 - 197 g/kg respectively. Silt/clay ratio was 1:2 at the top from 0 - 15cm. However, the observed variations in the particle size fractions due to treatments did not alter the soil textural class. Rather, it is the dominant particles from the parent material that influence the soil textural class as shown in Table 2 by total subsample mass.

Table 2: Particle size distribution of the treatment categories

Treatments	Soil (g/kg)	Silt (g/kg)	Clay (g/kg)
Untreated Soil	818	48	180
Pl 20 % + COCS	740	51	120
Pl 40 % + COCS	730	78	160
Pl 50 % + COCS	801	14	170

*Soil particle size distribution (0 - 15cm) at 8 weeks after treatments. Pl - Poultry litter; crude oil contaminated soil (COCS).

From Figure 1, it is can be inferred that there is a higher presence of sand then silt and clay in all the treatments including the untreated soil itself after 8weeks. In treatment, PL 50% + COCS, the presence of silt is comparably lower than that of the PL 20% + COCS, PL 40% +COCS and even the untreated soil. It is found that the sampled soil is Sandy loam in nature, which makes it suitable for agricultural purposes. Similarly, the initial

moisture content rose from 2 % at the beginning of the study to 18.4 % maximum among the soil treated with the poultry litter (PL 40 % + COCS) against 18.9 % recorded for untreated (control) soil sample.

Microorganisms require water for microbial growth and for the diffusion of nutrients and by-products during the degradation process, so if the soil is too dry, many microorganisms will die. If water content of the soil is too high, oxygen transfer to microorganisms will be resisted by the flooded soil and the rate of hydrocarbon degradation will be reduced. The optimum soil water content for bioremediation is dependent on the soil type. Generally, the optimum activity occurs when the soil moisture is 15 – 40% of the field capacity. When the moisture content is lower than 10% of the holding capacity, the bioactivity becomes marginal (Testa and Winegardener, 1991). Water was added to the entire experimental group so as to achieve an optimum moisture content of at least 17%. Based on the results observed, moisture content was optimum in all the treatment categories including the control.

Tables 2 and 3 show the results of the Total Microbial Count. For the total heterotrophic bacteria count (THBC), PL 50% + COCS has 1.5×10^5 CFU/g even greater than the THBC of the soil itself which is 1.2×10^4 CFU/g. The fungal count (FC) of PL 50% +COCS is also the highest with 1.6×10^4 CFU/g with the least fungal count being the poultry litter which is 1.1×10^3 CFU/g. The Total Coliform count (TCC) which is a water contamination test expressed in Coliform Microbial Density (CMD) indicates that 2.3×10^4 is present in PL 50% + COCS which is higher than the other treatments including the crude oil contaminated soil. The least TCC is that of PL 20% + COCS which indicated 1.5×10^3 cmd. The Clostridium count which is obtained to determine the significant Gram positive bacteria was found to be higher in the crude oil contaminated soil. It was found to be 1.4×10^3 CFU/g. Also, there were higher values of Hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria (HUB) and Hydrocarbon utilizing fungi (HUF) in the PL 50% + COCS which are 1.3×10^3 CFU/g and 7.0×10^2 CFU/g respectively.

Table 2: THBC, FC and TCC Counts

Samples	THBC (CFU/g)	FC (CFU/g)	TCC (cmd)
Untreated Soil	1.2×10^4	1.4×10^3	1.7×10^3
PL 20% + COCS	1.2×10^5	1.4×10^3	1.5×10^3
PL 40% + COCS	1.1×10^5	2.0×10^3	1.4×10^3
PL 50% +COCS	1.5×10^5	1.6×10^4	2.3×10^4
Poultry Litter	1.3×10^4	1.1×10^3	2.0×10^3

* THBC = Total heterotrophic bacterial count* FC = Fungal count * TCC =Total Coliform count

Table 3: CC, HUB and HUF counts

Samples	CC (CFU/g)	HUB (CFU/g)	HUF (CFU/g)
Untreated Soil	1.4 × 10 ³	1.2 × 10 ²	6.0 × 10 ²
PL 20% + COCS	1.0 × 10 ³	1.0 × 10 ²	1.5 × 10 ²
PL 40% + COCS	1.3 × 10 ³	1.0 × 10 ²	5.0 × 10 ²
PL 50% +COCS	1.0 × 10 ³	1.3 × 10 ³	7.0 × 10 ²
Poultry Litter	1.0 × 10 ²	-	-

* CC = Clostridium count * HUB = Hydrocarbon utilizing bacteria * HUF = Hydrocarbon utilizing fungi

The results of the total microbial count indicate that with a perfect blend of poultry litter and the contaminated soil i.e. PL 50% + COCS and preferably suggested, because there are improved results in the remediation of soils that are contaminated by heavy metals. The Coliform count indicates the extent of fecal matter present in the samples and in order to prevent health hazards, it is important that Coliform count should not be greater than 1000 colonies.

Microbial Isolates

The following heterotrophic microbial species were identified in the study: *Micrococcus sp.*, *Bacillus sp.*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Pseudomonas aerogmisa*, *Chromatium sp.*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Geotrichum candidum* as shown on Table 4.

The microbial density and diversity prevalent in the contaminated medium i.e. the soil sample played an important role in the reduction of pollutants

Table 4: Microbial isolates of COCS samples

Bacteria	Fungi
<i>Micrococcus sp.</i>	<i>Candida tropicalis</i>
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	<i>Geotrichum candidum</i>
<i>Pseudomonas aerogmosa</i>	
<i>Chromatin sp.</i>	

The occurrence and distribution of the diverse microbial isolates of the samples in Table 5 shows the presence (+) or absence (-) of the isolates in the samples.

From the results obtained of the samples, PL 50% + COCS and soil indicates the huge presence of bacterial isolates more than any other sample and also, the PL 50% +COCS and the soil indicates more presence of fungi isolates than any other sample.

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Table 5: Occurrence and distribution of the microbial isolates in all samples.

Isolates	PL 20% + COCS	PL 40% + COCS	PL 50% + COCS	Manure	Untreated Soil
<i>Micrococcus sp</i>	+	+	+	-	+
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	-	+	+	+	+
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Pseudomonas aerogmosa</i>	-	-	+	-	+
<i>Chromatin sp.</i>	-	-	-	-	+
<i>Candida tropicalis</i>	-	-	+	-	+
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	+	-	+	+	-
<i>Geotrichum candidum</i>	-	-	-	-	+

*+ = positive * - = negative

pH for untreated soil at baseline week (week one) was 5.0 while it was 7.6 for poultry litter as the nutrient additive. The results obtained at the end of the experiment indicate a range of 8.1 (week 1 PL 20% + COCS). These results show that pH in treatment categories was slightly higher than the control throughout the experiment although this difference was insignificant. The initial (0 week) and final (8 week) heavy metals concentration in the soil were obtained using the atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The values were compared with the normal and critical levels of concentration of the selected heavy metals shown in Tables 6 and 7 respectively.

Table 6: Initial concentration of heavy metal level at Week 0 (All values in ppm)

Metals	Cu	Fe	Mn	Pb	Cd	As	Cr	Ni	Mean	SD
Untreated Soil	3.57	6.84	9.07	1.21	1.26	3.95	3.81	3.76	4.18	2.477
PL 20% + COCS	4.06	6.75	8.90	1.40	1.40	3.00	3.70	3.40	4.08	2.411
PL 40% + COCS	3.76	6.47	8.80	1.56	1.56	2.80	3.50	3.05	3.94	2.180
PL 50% + COCS	3.45	6.55	8.60	1.10	1.10	2.05	3.18	3.16	3.65	2.468

Table 7: Initial concentration of heavy metal level at Week 8 (All values in ppm)

Metals	Cu	Fe	Mn	Pb	Cd	As	Cr	Ni	Mean	SD
Untreated Soil	3.43	6.63	8.88	1.00	1.17	3.96	3.73	3.64	4.05	2.448
PL 20% + COCS	0.53	0.64	0.70	0.67	0.51	1.85	1.35	1.35	0.95	0.466
PL 40% + COCS	0.62	0.61	0.63	0.63	0.50	1.51	1.20	1.01	0.84	0.329
PL 50% + COCS	0.43	0.50	0.47	0.55	0.41	0.68	0.76	0.83	0.58	0.119

Table 8: Summary of ANOVA at Week 0

Group	Count	Sum*	Average*	Variance*	Source of variation	SS*	Df*	MS*	F*	P-value*	F-Crit*
Untreated Soil	8	33.47	4.18	7.01	Between Groups	1.29	3	0.43	0.06	0.98	2.95
PL20%+COCS	8	32.61	4.08	6.64	Within Groups	188.24	28	6.72			
PL40%+COCS	8	30.50	3.94	6.24							
PL50%+COCS	8	29.19	3.65	6.99	Total	189.53	31				

Table 9: Summary of ANOVA at Week 8

Group	Count	Sum*	Average*	Variance*	Source of variation	SS*	Df*	MS*	F*	P-value*	F-Crit*
Untreated Soil	8	32.44	4.06	6.89	Between Groups	64.57	3	21.52	11.80	3.57E-05	2.95
PL20%+COCS	8	7.60	0.95	0.25	Within Groups	51.07	28	1.82			
PL40%+COCS	8	6.71	0.84	0.13							
PL50%+COCS	8	4.63	0.58	0.03	Total	115.64	31				

Note: * indicates that values were approximated to 2 decimal place

*SS = Sum of Squares, *Df = Degree of freedom, *MS = Mean Square, *F = Factor ratio

*P- value = probability value

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A one – way ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) proved the variation in the effectiveness of the different treatment categories in remediating crude oil contaminated soil. Tables 8 and 9 show that there are significant differences in the reduction of heavy metals in the soil by the different categories of soil treatment.

At a significance level of 0.05 (Adam and Mark Lund (2013), it can be inferred from Table 8 that the probability value (P- value) at 0.00035 is less than 0.05 the significance level i.e. $P < 0.05$ after 8 weeks of the study. There exists a huge variance of PL 50% + COCS from the significance level at 0.05 to be 0.025. This result proves that the treatment category, PL 50% + COCS proved to be the most effective in the reduction of the heavy metals concentration level in this study.

There was also a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between week 0 and week 8 for all the heavy metals analyzed in this study. Heavy metals concentration in the untreated soil did not reduce since there was no treatment or the addition of poultry litter made on it to reduce the heavy metals in it. In Table 10, the heavy metals concentration in soil treated with poultry litter by 20% i.e. for the ratio 20% of poultry litter to 80% of soil showed a significant reduction. From Table 10, after the application of poultry litter by 40% to soil in the ratio of 40% of poultry litter to 60% of soil, the heavy metals concentration in soil showed a significant reduction. There is a significant reduction in heavy metals concentration level in the soil after the application of poultry litter by 50% at the ratio 50% of poultry litter to 50% of soil.

Table 10: Heavy metals reduction after application of varying Poultry dung between week 0 – 8.

Heavy Metal	Initial Concentration at 0 Week (ppm, %)			Final Concentration at 8 Week (ppm, %)			Percentage increase observed (0 - 8Wk)	Significance between Treated and untreated Soil (P<0.05)
	PL 20%+ COCS	PL 40%+ COCS	PL 50%+ COCS	PL 20%+ COCS	PL 40%+ COCS	PL 50%+ COCS		
Copper (Cu)	4.06 (ppm) 100 %	3.76 (ppm) 100 %	3.45 (ppm) 100 %	0.53 (ppm) 86.90 %	0.62 (ppm) 83.50 %	0.43 (ppm) 87.54 %	3.57 – 3.40 (ppm) 3.92 %	Significance between treated and untreated Soil
Iron (Fe)	6.75 (ppm) 100 %	6.47 (ppm) 100 %	6.55 (ppm) 100 %	0.64 (ppm) 90.50 %	0.61 (ppm) 90.50 %	0.50 (ppm) 92.20 %	6.84 – 6.30 (ppm) 3.07 %	Significantly reduction in the treated Soil.
Manganese (Mn)	8.90 (ppm) 100 %	8.80 (ppm) 100 %	8.60 (ppm) 100 %	0.70 (ppm) 83.00 %	0.63 (ppm) 92.80 %	0.57 (ppm) 93.3 %	9.07 – 8.88 (ppm) 2.09 %	Significantly reduction in the treated Soil with 50%.
Lead (Pb)	1.40 (ppm) 100 %	1.56 (ppm) 100 %	1.10 (ppm) 100 %	0.67 (ppm) 52.10 %	0.63 (ppm) 59.60 %	0.55 (ppm) 49.72 %	1.21 – 1.00 (ppm) 17.08 %	Significantly less reduction in the treated Soil with 50%.
Cadmium (Cd)	1.25 (ppm) 100 %	1.23 (ppm) 100 %	1.24 (ppm) 100 %	0.51 (ppm) 59.20 %	0.50 (ppm) 59.3 %	0.41 (ppm) 67.0 %	1.26 – 1.17 (ppm) 7.14 %	Marginal significantly reduction in the treated Soil with 50%. Katerina <i>et al.</i> , (2004)

Arsenic (As)	3.00 (ppm) 100 %	2.80 (ppm) 100 %	2.05 (ppm) 100 %	1.85 (ppm) 38.80 %	1.50 (ppm) 46.10 %	0.68 (ppm) 66.80 %	3.95 – 3.93 (ppm) 0.51 %	Significantly reduction in the treated Soil with 50%. Katerina <i>et al.</i> , (2004)
Chromium (Cr)	3.70 (ppm) 100 %	3.50 (ppm) 100 %	3.18 (ppm) 100 %	1.85 (ppm) 50.00 %	1.20 (ppm) 65.70 %	0.76 (ppm) 76.10 %	3.81 – 3.73 (ppm) 2.10 %	High reduction with the 50% proportion. Chenu (2001)
Nickel (Ni)	3.40 (ppm) 100 %	3.05 (ppm) 100 %	3.16 (ppm) 100 %	1.35 (ppm) 60.30 %	1.01 (ppm) 67.00 %	0.83 (ppm) 73.70 %	3.76 – 3.64 (ppm) 3.20 %	High reduction with the 50% proportion. Chenu (2001)

Conclusion

The research findings indicate that bioremediation using growing microorganisms present in poultry litter used in this study can reduce the concentration of heavy metals in soil. The presence of consortia of microorganisms improved the metals scavenging properties and ensured continuity in the process irrespective of any external environmental fluctuations. However, choosing the right consortia depends on initial heavy metals concentration and should be carefully carried out as done in this study so as to ensure some microorganisms metabolism do not inhibit the growth of others.

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